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EDITORIAL NOTE

It is with immense pleasure and pride that we present to you the third issue of the Bauchi State University (BASUG) Law Journal, marking our second publication for the year. This issue stands as a testament to the tireless commitment of our contributors, whose scholarly work continues to push the boundaries of legal scholarship in Nigeria and beyond.

We are particularly elated by the diversity and depth of the submissions received for this edition, not only from across Nigeria but also from international scholars. The topics covered reflect the evolving and multifaceted nature of legal discourse in contemporary society.

These papers, among others, cover a vast range of legal fields, reflecting the dynamic interplay between law and society. We believe the breadth of scholarship featured in this issue will contribute meaningfully to academic discourse and legal practice.

We would like to extend our profound appreciation to the Faculty of Law, Sa'adu Zungur University, for their unwavering support as our publisher. Our sincere gratitude also goes to the Management of Sa'adu Zungur University for their continued encouragement and partnership in ensuring the success of this journal.

We are deeply indebted to the contributing authors for their invaluable research and dedication to advancing legal knowledge. Their work remains at the heart of what makes this journal a beacon of academic excellence.

Finally, we thank you, our esteemed readers, for your continued engagement with the BASUG Law Journal. It is through your readership that this publication finds purpose, and we hope that this issue serves as both a valuable resource and a source of inspiration for future legal thought and action.

Sincerely,

Prof. S. M. G Kanam
Chairman of Editorial Board and Dean
Faculty of Law,
Sa'adu Zungur University

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HEALTH RESPONSE FOR GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE SURVIVORS

By

Adekilekun Medinat Adeola*

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ABSTRACT

Gender-Based Violence (GBV) constitutes a profound global public health concern and a widespread violation of human rights, affecting individuals across diverse demographics, with a disproportionate impact on women and girls. GBV encompasses a spectrum of physical, sexual, psychological, and economic violations, and has only recently garnered significant research and policy attention. Despite its recognized severity, GBV persists, deeply entrenched in socioeconomic and cultural factors, including poverty, gender norms, and patriarchal structures. Effective health security and response strategies are crucial in addressing the immediate and long-term needs of GBV victims, encompassing immediate medical care, psychological support, counselling services, and social services to ensure comprehensive care and recovery. This study employed a multifaceted qualitative methodology to gather rich, contextual data on GBV. The approach comprised in-depth interviews with GBV survivors and social service workers to elicit detailed insights into their experiences and perspectives. Content analysis was applied to transcripts, notes, and documents to identify patterns, themes, and meanings. Additionally, case studies were examined to gain an in-depth understanding of individual experiences and responses. This comprehensive approach enabled the researchers to capture the complexities of GBV and identify key factors facilitating recovery and empowerment, providing a nuanced understanding of the issue. The findings emphasize the necessity of trauma-informed care, safe housing, economic empowerment, and continuous monitoring and evaluation to enhance response mechanisms. Through health responses, survivors tend to regain hope, significantly improving their health, productivity, and overall wellbeing. This paper advocates for a holistic approach integrating prevention, protection, and empowerment, ensuring victims receive comprehensive support to rebuild their lives.

KEYWORDS: Gender-Based Violence (GBV), Public Health, Socioeconomic and Cultural Factors, Health Security and Response, Trauma-Informed Care

1. INTRODUCTION

Gender-Based Violence (GBV) constitutes a profound global public health concern and a widespread violation of human rights, affecting individuals across diverse demographics, with a disproportionate impact on women and girls. GBV encompasses a spectrum of physical, sexual, psychological, and economic violations, and has only recently garnered significant research and policy attention. Despite its recognized severity, GBV persists, deeply entrenched in socioeconomic and cultural factors, including poverty, gender norms, and patriarchal structures. Effective health security and response strategies are crucial in addressing the immediate and long-term needs of GBV victims, encompassing immediate medical care, psychological support, counselling services, and social services to ensure comprehensive care and recovery.

Gender-based violence (GBV) is a pervasive issue that transcends cultural, geographical, and socioeconomic boundaries, impacting millions of individuals worldwide. It is defined as harmful acts directed at individuals based on their gender manifesting in various forms including physical, sexual, psychological, and economic violence. The term GBV is often used interchangeably with violence against women (VAW) and violence against women and girls (VAWG). However, GBV is gender-neutral and encompasses violence against individuals of any gender or sexual orientation.

1.1 Statement of Problem:

Despite global recognition of the severity of Gender-Based Violence (GBV), it remains a pervasive issue affecting millions of individuals worldwide, with women and girls being disproportionately affected. The medical sector, as the last resort for survivors, faces challenges in responding effectively to GBV, highlighting the need for improved interventions and support systems.

1.2 Research Objectives:

1. To explore the impact of GBV on survivors' physical and mental health, social, and economic well-being.

2. To examine the current response mechanisms of the health sector in addressing GBV.
3. To identify gaps and challenges in the health sector's response to GBV.
4. To propose strategies for improving the efficiency of the health sector in responding to GBV.

1.3 Methodology:

This study will employ a qualitative research design, using a multi-faceted approach to gather rich and contextual data. The methodology will include:

1. In-depth interviews with GBV survivors, healthcare providers, and social service workers.
2. Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) with survivors and community members.
3. Content analysis of transcripts, notes, and documents.
4. Case studies of individual experiences and responses.

This comprehensive approach will enable the researchers to capture the complexities of GBV and identify key factors facilitating recovery and empowerment.

1.4 Detailed Methodology:

This study utilized a qualitative research methodology, specifically a grounded theory approach, to deeply explore the lived experiences of GBV survivors and the effectiveness of health responses in aiding their recovery. Grounded theory was chosen because it allows for the development of theories directly rooted in the data, making it particularly useful for understanding complex social phenomena like GBV. Data were collected through in-depth, semi-structured interviews with GBV survivors who had accessed health services within the past year. These participants were purposively selected to ensure a diverse sample, representing different ages, socio-economic backgrounds, and geographic locations, including both urban and rural settings. In addition to survivors, healthcare providers, including doctors, nurses, and counsellors, were interviewed to gain insights into the challenges they face when treating GBV

survivors. The interviews, conducted over six months, each lasted between 60 and 90 minutes. Survivors were asked about their experiences with healthcare services, their recovery journey, and suggestions for improvement, while healthcare providers discussed their experiences delivering care and the systemic barriers they encounter. The data were analysed using a combination of open coding and axial coding. Open coding broke down the interview transcripts into key concepts and ideas, which were then reassembled during axial coding to explore relationships among these concepts. This iterative process helped to identify core themes and sub-themes related to the effectiveness of health responses, the specific needs of survivors, and gaps in service provision. Ethical considerations were rigorously observed, with participants providing informed consent and being assured of confidentiality and anonymity. The study's methodology was designed to ensure that the findings were deeply grounded in the participants' experiences, providing a solid foundation for the conclusions drawn.

1.5 Literature Review

The literature review underscores the gravity and intricacy of gender-based violence (GBV), highlighting its far-reaching consequences on physical and mental well-being, human rights, and societal welfare (Russo, 2019). A plethora of studies and reports from esteemed organizations, including the World Health Organization (WHO) and United Nations, have delved into the causes, effects, and interventions related to GBV (WHO, 2013; UN, 2015). Nevertheless, a notable gap persists in the literature concerning the health sector's response to GBV survivors.

While research has begun to emerge on the health implications of GBV and some interventions (Logan et al., 2015; Smythe et al., 2018), a more comprehensive and coordinated health response is needed to address the unique requirements of GBV survivors. Specifically, the literature review reveals gaps in:

1. Holistic health services: A dearth of research on integrated health services that cater to GBV survivors' multifaceted needs (Ashford & Feldman-Jacobs, 2010).
2. Healthcare provider capacity building: Inadequate training for healthcare providers in GBV response, resulting in suboptimal care and support (Dash & Singh, 2016).

3. Survivor-centric care: Limited emphasis on prioritizing survivors' needs and experiences in GBV response (Barnett et al., 2016).
4. Intersectional considerations: Insufficient attention to intersecting factors like age, disability, and socioeconomic status in GBV response (Muvumba-Sellström, 2015).
5. Resource-constrained settings: Limited research on GBV health responses in low- and middle-income countries (Bott et al., 2005).

The proposed research seeks to bridge these gaps by investigating effective health responses for GBV survivors, focusing on comprehensive, survivor-centred, and context-specific interventions.

2. MEANING AND NATURE OF GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE

Gender-based violence is one of the many forms of violence. Violence as defined by the WHO is *the intentional use of physical force or power, threatened or actual, against oneself, another person, or against a group or community that either results in or has a high likelihood of resulting in injury, death, psychological harm, mal-development or deprivation.*¹

From the above definition, it is important to note that violence does not always result in physical harm; the mere threat or potential for harm suffices to qualify as violence. Additionally, the impact of violence on both physical and psychological well-being and development is taken into account. As a result, the act of violence itself, as well as its subsequent effects, may not always be immediately observable.

Gender-based violence (GBV) is a particular form of violence that has been defined predominantly from the perspective of violence against women to underscore the pervasive threat of violence experienced by many women and girls on a daily basis. Gender inequality is so pervasive globally that women in all countries face discrimination and violence due to their gender, constituting the majority of GBV

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¹ World Health Organisation, 'The VPA approach' (2002) available at < www.who.int/groups/violenceprevention-alliance/approach > accessed on 07 October 2023.

survivors.² Women and girls bear a significant burden of violence, with an estimated 35% experiencing physical and/or sexual intimate partner violence (IPV) or sexual violence by a non-partner at some point in their lives.³ Thus, it has been defined by the United Nations in the Convention on Elimination of all forms of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW) using the term violence against women defined as *any act of gender-based violence that results in, or is likely to result in, physical, sexual or psychological harm or suffering to women, including threats of such acts, coercion or arbitrary deprivations of liberty, whether occurring in public or private life.*⁴

Similarly, the Council of Europe Convention on preventing and combating violence against women and domestic violence, colloquially known as the Istanbul Convention highlighted as the benchmark for international legislation on addressing gender-based violence, specifically uses GBV interchangeably with VAW, *gender-based violence against women.*⁵

However, there has been an increasing trend towards expanding the definition of GBV to encompass all individuals who experience violence based on their gender. For instance, the United Nations Office for the High Commissioner for Human Rights (UN OHCHR) highlights in their fact sheet on homophobic and transphobic violence that attacks on individuals due to their sexual orientation or gender identity are often motivated by a desire to punish those perceived as defying gender norms, constituting a form of gender-based violence.⁶ Similarly, the Caribbean and Vulnerable Communities Coalition (CVC) and UN Women assert that GBV typically occurs when individuals fail to conform to stereotypical gender expectations or when there are uneven power dynamics in relationships.⁷

² Inter-Agency Standing Committee, 'Guidelines for integrating gender-based violence interventions in humanitarian action: reducing risk, promoting resilience and aiding recovery' (2015) available at <https://gbvguidelines.org/wp/wp-content/uploads/2015/09/2015-IASC-Genderbased-Violence-Guidelines_lo-res.pdf> accessed on 07 October 2023.

³ World Health Organisation (WHO), 'Responding to Intimate Partner Violence and Sexual Violence Against Women – WHO clinical and policy guidelines' (2013)

⁴ Art. 1, Declaration on the Elimination of Violence against Women

⁵ European Institute of Gender equality, 'What is gender-based violence?' available at <<https://eige.europa.eu/gender-based-violence/what-is-gender-basedviolence>> accessed on 07 October 2023.

⁶ UN Office for High Commissioner on Human Rights (OHCHR), 'Fact Sheet: Homophobic and transphobic violence' available at <https://www.ohchr.org/Documents/Issues/Discrimination/LGBT/FactSheets/unfe-27-UN_Fact_Sheets_Homophobic_English.pdf> accessed on 15 October 2023.

⁷ Caribbean Vulnerable Communities Coalition (CVC), UN Women (2016)

The most commonly referenced definition of GBV according to UN Women in humanitarian settings aligns with the one adopted by the UN Inter-Agency Standing Committee (IASC) GBV Guidelines. This definition defines GBV as an umbrella term to mean *any harmful act perpetrated against a person's will, based on socially ascribed (gender) differences between males and females*.⁸ Thus, this definition encompasses violence against Gender Non-Conforming (GNC) individuals, as well as others within the LGBTQIA+ community, and violence involving men and boys often grounded in societal expectations of masculinities that either encourage or enable violence by and against men.

Also, the European Commission's Gender Equality in Sport: Proposal for Strategic Actions 2014–2020 provides the following definition of GBV: *violence directed against a person because of that person's gender (including gender identity/expression) or as violence that affects persons of a particular gender disproportionately*.⁹

Over time, organisational definitions of GBV have evolved to become more inclusive. It is therefore submitted that GBV refers to violence that is committed against someone based on their gender identity, gender expression or perceived gender with women and girls making up the vast majority of victims. It is a human rights violation, a public health challenge, and a barrier to civic, social, political, and economic participation. It undermines not only the safety, dignity, health status, and human rights of the millions of individuals who experience it, but also the public health, economic stability, and security of nations.

Noteworthy, the problem of GBV prevails all over the world. It encompasses a wide spectrum of harmful behaviours and actions that are inflicted upon individuals based on their biological sex or gender identity. Both males and females could be victims but studies have shown that the number of female victims is far greater than male

⁸ Inter-Agency Standing Committee, 'Guidelines for integrating gender-based violence interventions in humanitarian action: reducing risk, promoting resilience and aiding recovery' (2015).

⁹ European Commission, 'Gender equality in sport: Proposal for strategic actions 2014–2020' (2014) available at <https://ec.europa.eu/assets/eac/sport/events/2013/documents/20131203-gender/final-proposal-1802_en.pdf>, accessed on 15 October 2023.

victims,¹⁰ so each time the term is used, what readily comes to mind is violence against women and girls. It is characterized by its connection with unequal power dynamics between genders, hence, its prevalence against women. It is fundamentally rooted in the social construction of gender, which assigns roles, expectations, and privileges based on perceived norms associated with masculinity and femininity. GBV manifests when these gender norms are violated or reinforced through various forms of violence, including physical, sexual, psychological, and economic abuse. Central to its nature is the systemic oppression of women and other marginalized genders, perpetuated by patriarchal structures that prioritize male dominance and control.

Moreover, GBV is often fuelled by cultural norms, traditional practices, and societal attitudes that condone or excuse violence against women. These cultural beliefs may reinforce stereotypes about gender roles and behaviour, leading to the normalization of abusive practices such as child marriage, female genital mutilation, and honour killings. Such cultural factors contribute to the socialization of individuals into accepting or perpetrating acts of violence based on gender, further entrenching the cycle of GBV.

Furthermore, GBV is often characterized by its insidious nature, occurring across various settings, including homes, schools, workplaces, communities, and online platforms. It can take on subtle forms, such as macro-aggressions, as well as overt acts of violence, leaving survivors traumatized. The cyclical nature of GBV perpetuates a culture of fear, silence, and impunity, where perpetrators are rarely held accountable for their actions.

3. FORMS OF GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE

Gender-based violence encompasses a wide array of manifestations, ranging from the pervasive occurrence of intimate partner violence to incidents of violence occurring in tertiary institutions, online platforms among others. These diverse forms of violence are not mutually exclusive; multiple instances may co-occur and reinforce each other.

¹⁰ Isely Paul J, and David Gehrenbeck-Shim, 'Sexual assault of men in the community' (1997) 25(2) *Journal of Community Psychology*, 159.

The most commonly referenced forms of gender-based violence are physical, psychological, and sexual violence.¹¹ It is crucial to note that these forms of gender-based violence may occur individually or overlap and co-occur. According to the WHO typology of violence, gender-based violence encompasses various manifestations, including self-directed violence such as self-starvation (e.g., anorexia nervosa) and cutting,¹² interpersonal violence like domestic abuse and intimate partner sexual assault, and collective violence targeting women and girls as a group, such as female genital mutilation and ‘honour killings.’¹³

Premised on the above, the following forms of GBV are apparent.

i. Physical violence

Physical violence is a form of aggression that involves the intentional use of force to cause harm or injury to another person.¹⁴ It encompasses a wide range of actions, from minor incidents such as assaults, battery, to more severe acts such as grievous bodily harm. The effects of physical violence are brutal depending on the severity of the injury inflicted. Victims may experience immediate physical pain, bruises, cuts, broken bones, or even more serious injuries such as internal bleeding or organ damage. In extreme cases, physical violence can lead to permanent disability or death.¹⁵

Physical violence occurs in various settings, including domestic relationships, public spaces, workplaces, schools, or institutions. Perpetrators of physical violence may be intimate partners, family members, acquaintances, strangers, or individuals in positions of authority.

¹¹ Russo Nancy Felipe, ‘Violence against women: A global health issue’ in Qicheng Jing, Mark R. Rosenzweig, Gery d’Ydewalle, Houcan Zhang, Hsuan-Chih Chen, Kan Zhang (eds), *Progress in psychological science around the world* (Routledge, UK 2019) 181.

¹² Hanna Pickard, ‘Self-harm as violence: When victim and perpetrator are one’ in Marway, Herjeet, and Heather Widdows (eds), *Women and violence: The agency of victims and perpetrators* (Palgrave Macmillan, London, 2015) 71.

¹³ Krantz Gunilla, and Claudia Garcia-Moreno, ‘Violence against women’ (2005) 59(10) *Journal of Epidemiology & Community Health*, 818, available at <<http://doi.org/10.1136/jech.2004.022756>> accessed on 19 October 2023.

¹⁴ Allen Johnie J, and Craig A. Anderson, ‘Aggression and violence: Definitions and distinctions’ (2017) *The Wiley handbook of violence and aggression*, 1, available at <<http://www.craiganderson.org/wp-content/uploads/caa/abstracts/2015-2019/17AA2.pdf>> accessed on 19 October 2023.

¹⁵ Yacoub Sophie, Sergio Arellano, and Dennis Padgett-Moncada, ‘Violence related injuries, deaths and disabilities in the capital of Honduras’ (2006) 37(5) *Injury International Journal of the Care of the Injured*, 428, available at <[http://injuryjournal.com/article/S0020-1383\(05\)00471-7/abstract](http://injuryjournal.com/article/S0020-1383(05)00471-7/abstract)> accessed on 19 October 2023.

It is imperative to recognize that physical violence is not limited to acts committed with bare hands but can also involve the use of weapons or other objects to inflict harm. Additionally, physical violence can occur as a single isolated incident or as part of a pattern of ongoing abuse.¹⁶

ii. Sexual violence

Sexual violence is a deeply traumatic and harmful form of violence that involves any sexual act performed on an individual without their explicit and voluntary consent.¹⁷ This violation of bodily autonomy and personal boundaries can have devastating and long-lasting effects on the survivor's physical, emotional, and psychological well-being. Sexual violence encompasses a broad range of behaviours, including rape, sexual assault, molestation, coercion, harassment, and any other non-consensual sexual activity.¹⁸ It occurs within intimate relationships, familial settings, social gatherings, workplaces, or in public spaces.

The impact of sexual violence on survivors can be many. Physically, survivors may experience injuries, sexually transmitted infections (STIs), unwanted pregnancies, or other reproductive health consequences.¹⁹ Emotionally and psychologically, survivors may suffer from feelings of shame, guilt, fear, anxiety, depression, post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), and other mental health disorders.²⁰ They may also struggle with trust issues, difficulty forming intimate relationships, and challenges in their daily functioning.

¹⁶ Widom Cathy S, 'Does violence beget violence? A critical examination of the literature' (1989) 106(1)*Psychological bulletin*, 3, available at <<https://psycnet.apa.org/record/1989-36811-001>> accessed on 19 October 2023

¹⁷ Logan T.K, Robert Walker, and Jeniffer Cole, 'Silenced suffering: The need for a better understanding of partner sexual violence' (2015) 16(2)*Sage Journals*, 111, available at <<https://doi.org/10.1177/1524838013517560>> accessed on 21 October 2023.

¹⁸ Jejeebhoy Shireen J, and Sarah Bott, 'Non-consensual sexual experiences of young people: A review of the evidence from developing countries' (2003) available at <https://knowledgecommons.popcouncil.org/departments_sbsr-rh/526/> accessed on 21 October 2023.

¹⁹ Davis Kelly Cue, et al. 'Women's sexual violence victimization and sexual health: Implications for risk reduction' (2018)*Sexual assault risk reduction and resistance*, 379, available at <<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/B9780128053898000165>> accessed on 29 November 2023.

²⁰ Bayram Kuzgun Tubanur, 'The Association Between Posttraumatic Stress Disorder and Trauma-Related Guilt, Shame, Fear, and Sense of Control in Women with Sexual Trauma' (Ph.D Dissertation, Istanbul Arel University, Istanbul, Turkey 2018) p. 66.

It is essential to recognize that sexual violence is not solely about physical force or coercion; it can also involve manipulation, psychological pressure, blackmail, or exploitation of vulnerabilities. Moreover, sexual violence can occur across the lifespan, affecting individuals of all ages, genders, sexual orientations, races, ethnicities, and socioeconomic backgrounds.²¹

iii. Psychological violence

Psychological violence, also known as emotional or mental abuse, is a form of violence that targets a person's emotions, mental well-being, and sense of self-worth. Unlike physical violence, which causes visible harm, psychological violence inflicts damage on a person's psyche and emotional health. It can take various forms, including verbal threats, intimidation, manipulation, humiliation, degradation, and control tactics.

Psychological violence is inherently intertwined with physical and sexual violence but may also stand alone.²² One of the defining characteristics of psychological violence is its insidious nature. It often occurs in private, making it harder to detect and address.²³ Perpetrators of psychological violence may employ subtle tactics to undermine the victim's confidence, self-esteem, and autonomy. This can include gaslighting, where the abuser denies the victim's reality or undermines their perception of events, causing them to doubt their own sanity.

Psychological violence has long-lasting effects on the victim's mental health and well-being. It can lead to anxiety, depression, low self-esteem, and post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD).²⁴ Victims may experience feelings of worthlessness, helplessness, and hopelessness, which can impact their ability to function in daily life and maintain healthy relationships.

²¹ Tarzia Laura, 'Toward an ecological understanding of intimate partner sexual violence' (2021) 36(23) *Journal of Interpersonal Violence*, 117, available at <<https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/pdf/10.1177/0886260519900298>> accessed on 9 November 2023.

²² Russo Nancy Felipe, 'Violence against women: A global health issue' in Qicheng Jing, Mark R. Rosenzweig, Gery d'Ydewalle, Houcan Zhang, Hsuan-Chih Chen, Kan Zhang (eds), *Progress in psychological science around the world* (Routledge, UK 2019) 187.

²³ Follingstad Diane R, 'Rethinking current approaches to psychological abuse: Conceptual and methodological issues' (2007) 12(4) *Aggression and Violent Behavior*, 439 available at <<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S1359178907000031>> accessed on 12 November 2023.

²⁴ Duxbury Fiona, 'Recognising domestic violence in clinical practice using the diagnoses of posttraumatic stress disorder, depression and low self-esteem' (2006) 56(525) *British Journal of General Practice*, 294, available at <<https://bjgp.org/content/bjgp/56/525/294.full.pdf>> accessed on 17 November 2023.

It is noteworthy that psychological violence is just as harmful as physical violence, and it should not be dismissed or trivialized.

iv. Economic violence

Economic violence is a form of abuse that targets a person's financial resources and economic independence to exert control and power over them. It takes various forms, including property damage, financial exploitation, economic coercion, and sabotage of financial resources.²⁵ Unlike other forms of violence, economic violence may not leave visible scars but can have long-lasting effects on the victim's well-being and autonomy.²⁶

One common manifestation of economic violence is financial exploitation, where the perpetrator exploits the victim's financial resources for their own gain. This can include stealing money or property, coercing the victim into giving them control over their finances, or preventing the victim from accessing their own funds.

Economic violence is often intertwined with other forms of abuse, such as domestic violence and intimate partner violence. Perpetrators may use economic control as a tactic to maintain power and control over their victims, making it difficult for them to leave abusive situations or seek help.²⁷ Thus, the consequences of economic violence can be severe and far-reaching. Victims may experience financial instability, poverty, and homelessness as a result of the abuse. They may also suffer from feelings of helplessness, dependence, and low self-esteem, making it challenging to break free from the cycle of abuse.

4. CAUSES OF GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE

²⁵ Corrie Tanya, 'Economic abuse: Searching for solutions' (2013) <https://goodshep.org.au/wp-content/uploads/2020/12/economic-abuse_final-report.pdf> accessed on 21 November 2023.

²⁶ Postmus Judy L, et al. 'Economic abuse as an invisible form of domestic violence: A multicountry review' (2020) 21(2) *Sage Journals*, 261 available at <<https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.1177/1524838018764160>> accessed 29 November 2023.

²⁷ Postmus Judy L, et al. 'Understanding economic abuse in the lives of survivors' (2012) (27) (3) *Journal of Interpersonal Violence*, 411-430, available at <https://www.academia.edu/download/45416925/Understanding_Economic_Abuse_in_the_Live20160506-12552-1gsku4r.pdf> accessed on 2 December 2023.

The issue of GBV is a cankerworm that has eaten deeply into the very fabric of our societies worldwide. While it manifests in different forms, its underlying causes are numerous, namely;

i. Gender Inequality

One of the primary underlying causes of GBV is gender inequality, based in discriminatory gender norms, stereotypes, and power imbalances that privilege men over women. In patriarchal societies, men are often accorded greater social, economic, and political power, while women and other marginalized genders are systematically disadvantaged and oppressed.²⁸ This unequal distribution of power perpetuates the belief that men are entitled to control women and reinforces the normalization of violence against them.

ii. Economic Disempowerment

Economic inequalities and poverty exacerbate the risk of GBV, as individuals experiencing financial hardship may be more vulnerable to exploitation and coercion. Economic dependence on abusive partners can trap survivors in abusive relationships, making it difficult for them to leave or seek help.²⁹ Furthermore, unequal access to economic opportunities and resources can perpetuate cycles of violence and hinder survivors' ability to rebuild their lives.

iii. Structural Factors

Structural factors, including discriminatory laws, inadequate access to justice, and weak enforcement of protective measures, contribute to the perpetuation of GBV. Legal and institutional frameworks often fail to adequately address the needs of

²⁸ Wood, Hannelie J, 'Gender inequality: The problem of harmful, patriarchal, traditional and cultural gender practices in the church' (2019) 75(1) *HTS Teologiese Studies/Theological Studies* available at <<https://www.ajol.info/index.php/hts/article/download/214561/202368>> accessed on 11 December 2023.

²⁹ Şimşek Altın Asli, 'Eliminating Economic Violence against Women for Gender Equality: Empowering Women through Human Rights Based Approach' in Yenilmez M. Ince, and Onur B. Çelik (eds), *A comparative perspective of women's economic empowerment* (Routledge, UK 2019)115.

survivors or hold perpetrators accountable for their actions, leading to impunity and further victimization.³⁰

iv. Impunity and Lack of Accountability

Perpetrators of GBV often face minimal consequences for their actions due to impunity, inadequate legal frameworks, and failures in law enforcement and judicial systems. The lack of accountability for perpetrators sends a message that violence against women is tolerated and perpetuates cycles of abuse.³¹ Additionally, societal attitudes that blame and shame survivors for the violence they experience further contribute to the normalization of GBV and hinder efforts to hold perpetrators accountable.³²

5. HEALTH RESPONSES TO GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE

In many societies, GBV victims often endure suffering in silence. Health organisations are important in breaking this silence and providing essential care to individuals who may otherwise continue to endure violence and its associated health impacts. In recent years, there has been a growing recognition of the essential role that healthcare systems play in responding to GBV, both in terms of immediate medical care for survivors and in providing long-term support for their physical and psychological well-being. Health professionals frequently serve as the first point of contact for survivors of violence and, as respected members of society, possess the potential to influence societal perceptions by framing violence as a health issue. This approach acknowledges that GBV is not solely a social or legal issue but also a public health concern that requires a coordinated and comprehensive response from healthcare providers and institutions. The health sector has a unique opportunity to contribute to the prevention, identification, and management of GBV, thereby improving the overall health outcomes and quality of life for survivors. Health responses may include:

³⁰ Mills Elizabeth, et al. 'Turning the tide: The role of collective action for addressing structural and gender-based violence in South Africa' (2015) *Institute of Development Studies, February* available at <<https://www.academia.edu/download/65140938/Gill5.pdf>> accessed on 13 December 2023.

³¹ Muvumba Sellstrom Angel, 'Stronger than justice: armed group impunity for sexual violence' (Ph.D dissertation, Department of Peace and Conflict Research Uppsala University 2015) p. 51.

³² Barnett Jessica Penwell, Eleanor Maticka-Tyndale, and Trocaire Kenya, 'Stigma as social control: gender-based violence stigma, life chances, and moral order in Kenya' (2016) 63(3) *Social problems*, 447, available at <<https://doi.org/10.1093/socpro/spw012>> accessed on 21 December 2023.

1. Immediate Medical Care

Emergency Treatment: providing immediate and first aid medical attention to victims of GBV is crucial to address any physical injuries they may have sustained. This initial response involves treating wounds, fractures, and other injuries promptly to prevent further health complications. Beyond physical treatment, healthcare providers must also consider the victim's sexual and reproductive health. Access to emergency contraception is imperative to prevent unwanted pregnancies that could result from sexual violence.³³

Similarly, post-exposure prophylaxis (PEP) for HIV and other sexually transmitted infections (STIs) should be administered as soon as possible to mitigate the risk of infection. This comprehensive approach not only addresses the immediate physical health needs of the victim but also helps reduce the long-term health consequences associated with GBV.³⁴

Forensic Examination: a thorough forensic examination is another limb of immediate medical care to GBV victims. This process involves collecting evidence that can be used in legal proceedings to hold the perpetrator accountable. It is essential that this examination is conducted with the utmost respect for the victim's consent and comfort, recognising the potential for traumatisation. Thorough documentation and the secure preservation of physical evidence, such as clothing, perpetrators' DNA, biological samples, and photographic evidence of injuries, are crucial steps in holding perpetrators accountable for their actions. The integrity of this evidence is paramount, as it can play a pivotal role in the prosecution of GBV cases. Achieving this largely depends on immediate health intervention and response.³⁵

2. Psychological Support

³³ Smy the Dee, et al. 'Caught between policy and practice: health and justice responses to gender-based violence' (2018) *Crime, violence and injury prevention in South Africa: data to action. Tygerberg: Medical Research Council-University of South Africa Crime Violence and Injury Lead Programme*, 150.

³⁴ Shukla Shruti, Jessy Amarachi Ezebuihe, and Janina Isabel Steinert, 'Association between public health emergencies and sexual and reproductive health, gender-based violence, and early marriage among adolescent girls: a rapid review' (2023) 23(1) *BMC public health*, 117.

³⁵ Ashford Lori and Charlotte Feldman-Jacobs, 'The crucial role of health services in responding to gender-based violence' (2010) Agency for International Development.

Crisis Counselling: offering immediate psychological support is another important health security and response in helping GBV victims cope with the trauma they have experienced. Crisis counselling provides a safe space for victims to express their emotions, fears, and concerns immediately after the incident. This immediate intervention can significantly alleviate acute stress and anxiety.³⁶ Healthcare providers play an important role in this process and must be trained in trauma-informed care to ensure their interactions are characterized by due empathy. Trauma-informed care involves understanding the widespread impact of trauma, recognizing the signs and symptoms of trauma in patients, and responding by integrating this knowledge into practice.³⁷ This approach helps to avoid traumatization and builds trust between the healthcare provider and the victim, fostering a supportive environment where the victim feels heard and safe.

Long-term Mental Health Services: beyond crisis counselling, it is essential to provide ongoing counselling and therapy to address the long-term psychological impacts of GBV. Long-term mental health services are necessary to help victims work through complex emotional and psychological issues, such as depression, anxiety, post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), and other trauma-related conditions. Continuous therapy can help victims develop coping strategies, rebuild their self-esteem, and regain a sense of control over their lives.³⁸

3. Community Awareness and Prevention

Conducting public awareness campaigns, seminars are essential for educating communities about the realities and consequences of GBV. These campaigns can dispel myths, challenge stereotypes, and inform the public about the signs of GBV and available support services.³⁹

³⁶ Dash Rozaleen and M. Meghachandra Singh, 'Strengthening role of health sectors in gender based violence'(2016)3(6) *Int J Community Med Public Heal*, 1341.

³⁷ Sperlich Mickey, Patricia Logan-Greene, and Adair Finucane, 'Adopting a trauma-informed approach to gender-based violence across the life course' (2021) *Understanding gender-based violence: An essential textbook for nurses, healthcare professionals and social workers*, 185.

³⁸ Gevers Anik, and Elizabeth Dartnall, 'The role of mental health in primary prevention of sexual and gender-based violence' (2014)7(1) *Global health action*, 24741.

³⁹ Bott Sarah, Andrew Morrison, and Mary Ellsberg, 'Preventing and responding to gender-based violence in middle and low-income countries: a global review and analysis' (2005) available at <<https://books.google.com/books?hl=en&lr=&id=bHuoNOV1MGUC&oi=fnd&pg=PA3&dq=Bott,+S.,+Morrison,+A.,+%26+Ellsberg,+M.+%282005%29.+Preventing+and+responding+to+gender->

6. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This discourse on GBV highlights the crucial role of health security and responses in addressing this pervasive issue. The healthcare sector serves as a vital frontline responder, providing essential medical care, psychological support, and advocacy for survivors. Meticulous documentation and secure preservation of physical evidence are imperative in holding perpetrators accountable and securing justice for survivors. The health sector acts as a crucial link between survivors and the legal system, facilitating the collection and utilization of evidence to prosecute perpetrators and deter future incidents of violence.

To strengthen health responses to GBV, several recommendations emerge. Firstly, enhance training programs for healthcare providers to identify, document, and respond to GBV cases sensitively and effectively. Develop standardized protocols and guidelines within healthcare institutions for consistent and confidential collection and preservation of physical evidence. Inter-sectorial collaboration between healthcare, law enforcement, legal services, and community-based organizations is also important for streamlining the process of collecting and utilizing evidence in GBV cases.

In Mexico, a successful model for integrated attention to victims and survivors of sexual violence has been developed through collaboration between public hospitals, health units, and local and international organizations. This model includes violence detection, medical and counselling services, information registration, and referral to legal and social services. Extensive training programs have been implemented, resulting in significant advancements in institutionalizing a health systems response to women survivors of violence.

Additional recommendations include launching public awareness campaigns to reduce stigma, increase reporting rates, and empower survivors to access care and support services. Allocate adequate resources to GBV response programs within the healthcare sector to ensure sustainability and effectiveness of survivor-centred interventions. Finally, invest in research to evaluate the impact of health responses to

based+violence+in+middle+and+low-income+countries:+a+global+review+and+analysis&ots=tOXY-UFFLJ&sig=SbZjjds1FDvkAo3-clPAGLQnUW8> accessed on 7 January 2024.

GBV and identify areas for improvement to advance understanding and enhance ability to address this complex issue effectively.